

Hypersensitivity to Covid-19 vaccines confirmed

Despite the continuous evaluation for suitability by the FDA - Food and Drug Administration and EFSA, with the enormous quantity and variability of substances used such as additives, preservatives, excipients, in industrial manufacturing, which have nothing to do with nutrition. Using basic arithmetic in the sum function, a cumulative datum emerges, with multiple elements in the same body, such as multiple presences, at the same time, with elements that are also likely to contrast with each other, due to excessive industrialization and quantity of additives, about 3,000, to the detriment of everyone and in particular, for

those with the presence of the MTHFR of one or more alleles in all its forms, metabolically not prepared for transformation or use. This load of additive substances in the various industrialized products has been shown to produce adverse reactions, both small and large, every day of life, shown here:

- A: The **daily accumulation** in every single human being of the substances introduced into the body;
- B: The **multiple diversity** of finding different substances in the single product introduced into the body;
- C: The **evaluation** by the innate survival system, which reacts and repels the enemy;

On the basis of these elements, the body rejects the continuous toxic actions introduced into everyday life, air, food, drugs, by industrialized man.

CLINICAL CASE

Spain (Madrid): Woman, aged 30, experienced an immediate reaction following the first dose of the Pfizer SARS-CoV2 vaccine. The reaction was confirmed by Skin prick test (SPT).

A previous history of childhood hepatitis B virus, treated with interferon and chronic spontaneous urticaria occurred in 2019, controlled through an antihistamine treatment every 6 hours.

However, he had never seen reactions with other drugs in the past. Unfortunately, after 5 minutes of inoculation he developed itchy edematous lesions on the trunk, dyspnoea and dizziness.

Through a dose of adrenaline, a substance belonging to catecholamines, after about 30 minutes.

After about 18 hours, he developed extensive edema in the injected arm, from shoulder to hand. Taken to the emergency room, with the appropriate treatment conditions returned to normal after 2 hours.

One week later, the SPT tests for PEG and the polysorbates contained in the vaccines were performed at the allergology unit. The various tests and controls revealed that the patient had reacted to excipients contained in vaccines. The reliability of our observation, explain the authors, is reinforced by the report of other similar cases, concerning reactions to PEG and Polysorbates, therefore it will be necessary to understand the cross-reactivity patterns between inactive ingredients in Covid 19 vaccines, so that they can be provided. safe operations for patients allergic to polysorbates and PEGs. (note1)

Nature has endowed us with a superior defense to survive you have increasingly dangerous adverse signs, following the insistence on ingestion, inoculation, respiration, from the environment, to food to drugs of these substances, given the physiology of human nutrition for sustain living.

The research presented here, following the socio-economic-health implication, for survival, also given the chaotic pandemic, it leads every single human being to take one of two possible directions: the path of synthetic substances or the path of natural substances. The evaluation of the research highlights the adversities to the body, endangering daily survival through strong homeostatic stress, unbalancing the maintenance of vital balance.

Insights

If it is true that the first barrier in epidemiology is given by a healthy environment, by natural nutrients, suited to life support, it is equally true that the well-being of the body, for several decades, is merely an illusion, since the persistence of inserting excipients, preservatives, additives, adjuvants, everywhere, especially in foods and drugs, has promoted a powerful acceleration to adverse reactions of various degrees.

It is therefore evident that industrial transformations at any level, in synthetic substances such as **Polysorbates, Pegs**, wherever present, cause damage and structural transformations to the environment and inside living beings, starting from metabolism and epigenetic mechanisms. . The slow continuous "**aggression**", protracted over time on everyone, without exception, will help substances not suitable for human nutrition, making life difficult for man, who will be perennially ill.

This scheme, for some time has produced and produces, a continuous violence to the "body", silently and not only, making him a "slave" to the choices made.

Make food or other substances beautiful and attractive, just to attract aesthetically and make money, it follows a nutritional and intellectual depredation, breaking down one's defenses, leading the immune system to go crazy, going against oneself. The continuous stressor does not allow the body to be able to defend itself, repair itself, live. Therefore, the attraction through aesthetics, combined with the rapid internal deterioration of the elements, leads to continuous purchases, stealing from the community even one's own economy, in addition to that of health, without the possibility of freely choosing the way to heal oneself according to one's predispositions. innate genetics. An oxidized apple, ugly to look at, is very nutritious, while an apple that is always beautiful, shiny, fake, "toxic" will be of little use, that of being harmful.

The difficulty of the two elements is to maintain a correct balance between them, calling into question a third element, which must necessarily be incorruptible and impartial if you do not want to end up like the "Dinosaurs".

Inserting synthetic or biosimilar substances everywhere, passing them off as natural and nutritious, is no longer humanly acceptable since the body of the living being is inviolable. The continuous adverse reactions, **anaphylactoid**, are danger signals for the human being, since the body is endowed by its nature with universal survival defenses. Continuously give a drop of "poison" every day, that is, substances that are useless for the human being, with the hope of accustoming the body to accepting a foreign element, useful in the future to do something else.

This system of life, these methods has forgotten an elementary operation, the sum " + " .

By continuously introducing "**synthetic**" substances , in small doses, being the same everywhere, starting from toothpastes to fruit and medicines of all kinds, we must not forget that the accumulation makes up the sum.

Every hour, day, month, year, over time, they accumulate, adding up becoming very toxic elements, from heavy metals to viruses, bacteria, fine dust, nanoparticles, which inevitably lead the body to its reaction, given by the accumulation of toxicity, **in fact we are a bucket of garbage, difficult to dispose of and impossible to really cure**, but only to "milk", and here it is

that the body rebels and you have us before we go to the other side, so we are already with one foot in the pit, everyone. This accumulation leads to continuous adverse reactions, precisely because of this introductory method drop by drop, in an attempt to addict the person. Fortunately, we are not all the same.

Insights from the American College of Allergy, Asthma, highlight that there is currently no testing protocol for COVID-19 PEG, polysorbate, or mRNA vaccines, lacking predictive values and safety data from skin tests. [3]

The question arises: where do we live! How is it possible to protect and prevent damage to everyone's health.

In support, here is the link of a list that proves this heap: "man is killing man".

To try to help, a functional predictive test is planned, indicating the tolerability of the exposed elements to be tested.

Link to the list of drugs containing Polysorbates, PEG and not:

<https://www.aovr.veneto.it/documents/1977609/1977858/Farmaci+con+o+senza+PEG+%26+Polisorbato+80.pdf/32fef1e4-4b27-478b-9008-1828dc438909?version=1.0>

AIFA: Report number 2 on the surveillance of COVID-19 vaccines - "The main culprit was polyethylene glycol (PEG), also called macrogol, one of the components present in the lipids that surround mRNA and which is also present in other drugs and products non-pharmaceuticals of common daily use. Based on the available data, hypersensitivity reactions to PEG are rare and difficult to investigate because standardized tests are not available for diagnosis. For the moment, therefore, the evaluation of vaccination risk in people with suspected allergy to PEG must be essentially based on clinical history [18,19]

Link: https://www.aifa.gov.it/documents/20142/1315190/Rapporto_soruardia_vaccini_COVID_19_2.pdf

18, 2021. JAMA 2021. doi: 10.1001 / jama.2021.1967. 18 Turner PJ et al. WAO Anaphylaxis Committee. COVID-19 vaccine-associated anaphylaxis: A statement of the World Allergy Organization Anaphylaxis Committee. World Allergy Organ J. 2021; 14 (2): 100517. 19 Sellaturay P et al. Polyethylene Glycole-Induced Systemic Allergic Reactions (Anaphylaxis). J Allergy Clin Immunol 2021; 9 (2): P670 - 675.

Note1: Pérez-Codesido S, Rosado A, Alonso-Díaz-de-Durana MD, AlfayaArias T, González-Moreno A, Tejedor Alonso - Allergy Unit, University Hospital of the Alcorcón Foundation, (Madrid), Spain

[1] Sources: J Investig Allergol Clin Immunol 2021; vol. 31 (6): 524-525 doi: 10.18176 / jiaci.0718 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8577302/#R25>

[2] <http://www.jiaci.org/summary/vol31-issue6-num2392>

[3] <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/labs/pmc/articles/PMC7825848/>

Insights

Factsheet: Polysorbates are synthetic additives (E432 - E436) produced from sorbitol (E420). They are effective emulsifiers used found in dairy foods, coconut milk, soups, sauces and dietary supplements. Various studies, conducted on mice, suggest that the consumption of these additives could increase the permeability of the intestinal barrier and thus favor chronic inflammatory diseases of the intestine, an increase in adiposity (metabolic syndrome) and

development of diabetes. These additives could also disturb the balance of the intestinal flora, promoting autoimmune reactions. The chronic intestinal inflammation caused by these emulsifiers could eventually favor the onset of colon cancer.

Products in which it may be contained

In almost all food categories, with limits. In particular flavored products based on fermented milk, products similar to milk and cream, fat emulsions for baking, ice creams, coconut milk, confectionery products (only sugar-based, chewing-gum, decorations, coatings and fillings), fine baked goods, soups and broths, emulsified sauces, diet foods intended for special medical purposes and for weight control, desserts, food supplements. In point are the doses producing a bad assimilation of iron, residues such as iron oxide, dioxane and ethylene glycol are harmful to health. Importantly, people intolerant to propylene glycol should avoid the additive group E430 to E436. ADI DOSE: 25 mg per kg of body weight

Polysorbate 80, also known as Tween80, is a detergent (surfactant) used to pass certain drugs or chemicals across the blood brain barrier. This season's flu vaccine, for the US market, made by the company in charge with polysorbate 80, in childhood vaccines, has potentially serious side effects. **MF59**, polysorbate 80, squalene, another dangerous ingredient, can be found in various adjuvant vaccines. Squalene is an adjuvant marketed in vaccines in Europe and other countries, not yet approved by the FDA as an ingredient for vaccines distributed in the United States. The question is whether the various effects are also found in humans. Unfortunately, there is a glaring lack of research in this area, as it is thought to evaluate the dangers of the ingredients used, knowing that they can use the immunity sanctioned by the US government against liability for any damages. On the package insert of all influenza vaccines we could only read that **"they have not been**

evaluated for carcinogenic or mutagenic potential, or for impaired fertility".

Cancer researchers examined the effects of Tween80 on the in vitro metabolism of cancer cells and found that the detergent caused a marked increase in cell permeability, creating potential insertion into cells.

Given the attacks and violence perpetrated continuously, through the notices of the various multiple adverse reactions, abundantly documented in the literature, they are clearly obscured, modified, passing them as normality and people's truth, inserting extraneous elements drop by drop, hoping that the body will be habitual, but nature rebels and defends itself in various ways from the most banal to the most dangerous and no one will be excluded, if they do not avoid the excesses not tolerated by such environmental, food and medical toxicities, which turn on anyone and everywhere. The solution is to support nature and permanent detoxification, really and not in a fictitious way, hiding behind acronyms, digital codes and regulations, the first single judge to decide is the body and mind of the human being, the person who is involute.

These acts, invasive of continuous substances, of no nutritional usefulness, are nothing short of immediately condemnable, throwing away the key. The cellular indoctrination system is based on a principle. PSO: Little, Often, Everywhere, slowly accustoming the body to a slow torture to get it accustomed, feeding it in small steps "to toxic food obedience". This flood of additives, excipients, preservatives, adjuvants, etc. said several times and present everywhere, they have only one purpose, to make man a slave (for example, active and passive smoking).

Therefore, before placing one's own winning thesis on collective health, it is good to point out that this depends on the food and nutritional health of every living being in a natural way and without elements, synthetic or bio-similar without effective natural nutritional nourishment.

The fault ... the bad health, economic and social policies, increasingly oppressive, without real protection on health, before rights, without substances that are really useful for the body, with elements that are more and more harmful than nutritional, inhaled and taken by all, through breathing and feeding. This is a collective suicide, a crime against life, humanity a submission, through microscopic molecules, placed everywhere for years, to make them become rules for their own ends, certainly not for public health and even less for individual health.

Through reading and documentation, through reading, among the many acronyms and different names in the labels, which always lead us to the same elements, improperly regulated without calculating the accumulation of the many substances we use every day, symbolically regularized by numbers, from heavy metals to excipients, where it is the heap that damages everyone on a daily basis: from jurists to peasants, from doctors to patients, from workers to families.

It is a known history that one does not want to admit, that of a severe allergic reaction (eg. Anaphylaxis) or other multiple unexplained reactions, to the continuous "**synthetic**" components in the air, water, foods, drugs, products beauty and personal care (toothpastes, soaps, perfumes,) and of course also in experimental mRNA vaccines, in attempting to counteract infection from coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19). mRNA vaccines contain immunostimulating molecules, such as COVID-19 mRNA lipid nanoparticles (LNP), high molecular weight polyethylene glycol (PEG) and polysorbate 80. [1].

It is important to evaluate, before each vaccination, the likelihood of an adverse or allergic reaction to COVID-19 mRNA vaccines, starting with its excipients. To know everything it will be necessary for your health, to perform preliminary examinations and visits, on this topic, a topic discussed with Prof. Giulio Tarro.

"Dear Dr. Barone, thank you for your email. ... Since the importance of natural treatments is known as already reported by the Chinese delegation, last February in Italy, I thank you for your observation which can also be useful for the subjects in an interesting percentage who are carriers of this mutation, especially for transmission to children and the risk of complications in compulsory vaccinations. Cordiality Giulio Tarro lives on Mon 25 Jan 2021 at 7:09 pm "Link <https://www.pagineonline.org/archives/4090>

Therefore, it is of fundamental importance to reactivate the RDG020 MTHFR in the list of complex diseases, perhaps mysterious, never understood by allopathic medicine, since they are part of Mathematical Medicine Natural with Complex structures which does not mean complicated "(Prof.

Giuseppe Genovesi), to which people have always turned, finding a wall of lack of knowledge or worse still the total superficiality to the detriment of individual health.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BvbSKv73fLg&ab_channel=LuigiQuintavalle

Of all this, there are thousands of people who can testify, who have worsened, in the absence of knowledge and treated with other synthetic chemistry and not with alternative therapies, the only ones suitable for such hereditary cases, mutations that involve in first the food, their contents, increasingly lacking in true natural elements, and not synthetic, undermining public health. Therefore, people with the MTHFR mutation, with the various permutable alleles, must stay away as much as possible from synthetic products of all kinds, not suitable for their genetic match.

Therefore it is of fundamental importance to pass the amendment set aside on the MTHFR shown here - Source: <https://www.senato.it/japp/bgt/showdoc/print/17/Emend/01036363/01035798/0>

The excipients, adjuvants, preservatives, all elements that are enemies of public health, of the community. A scourge of society so small as to penetrate everything, up to our DNA, in fact

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technical data sheets of the producers of vaccine excipients, complex acronyms not known by many, hide their true negative nature. The peoples of the earth have accepted with their signature, the delivery of this negativity. The cards clearly mention that the components highlighted are not approved for human use or therapy. [2]

This "anomaly", served up to humans, finds confirmation in science through mathematics, demonstrating the real adversities, harmful to humans, making it weak and toxic, putting the process of methylation to the test, in fact the IgE immunoglobulins are persistent elements towards the PEG, since they are of high molecular weight, capable of acting on the surface. It is now certain that even more complex adverse events, such as anaphylaxis, after vaccination with COVID-19 mRNA, appeared immediately after vaccinations, aggravated with allergic-type reactions, highlighted during phase 3 trials in clinical studies. bringing out allergological processes on people reactive to vaccine excipients, such as polyethylene glycol (PEG) and Polysorgato 90, ACL-0159, ACL-0315, TC-102, etc. Sources: <https://www.pagineonline.org/archives/4576>

The protection of public health does not lie in the distinction between "vaccinated and unvaccinated" but between people who take care of their health through food as natural as possible, certainly not through aesthetics and therefore those who do not, for poverty or for other reasons, contribute to negativizing public health, as well as continuing toxicity

environmental and food increasingly deficient in nutrients, due to economic chemical industrialization, which governments have long been unable to solve for various reasons of interest.

From here a great chapter opens about the additives, preservatives, adjuvants and excipients present in addition to toxic metals, including the first in the ranking of silver, followed by mercury, lead, aluminum and nickel to other elements of radioactive origin (cesium) often found in autistic children.

From this it follows that our life is constantly in danger and any virus, bacteria or other element can strike as and when it wants due to the exaggerated use of synthetic chemicals and drugs that do not solve the problem at the root, but only for a short period of time, making us increasingly weak and vulnerable, as a result of the continuous depreciation of the immune system, not producing antibodies as a result of these industrialized synthetic elements. Therefore

the only source where we all go to draw to live, to protect our health and heal ourselves is nature.

It needs to return to mother earth, protecting it at all costs, the one that provides everyone with Air, Water, Food... Life.

With reference to the defenses against epidemic or pandemic attacks, plants have shown their superiority, in mitigating such possible events, whether natural or engineered, given by creation, which man often tends to replace, creating discomfort and death, hiding behind the fake words and statistics, touting that the benefits outweigh the risks, the famous adverse reactions.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known conflicts of interest or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this document.

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REFERENCES

- Pardi N, Hogan MJ, Porter FW, Weissman D. mRNA vaccines - a new era in vaccinology. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 2018; 17: 261-279. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Walsh EE, Frenck RW, Jr, Falsey AR, et al. . Safety and immunogenicity of two candidates for the *English N* RNA-based COVID-19 vaccine *J Med* 2020; 383: 2439-2450. [Free [article of PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Laczko D, Hogan MJ, Toulmin SA, et al. . A single immunization with nucleoside-modified mRNA vaccines elicits strong cellular and humoral immune responses against SARS-CoV-2 in mice. *Immunity* 2020; 53: 724-732. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Corbett KS, Edwards DK, Leist SR, et al. . Design of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccines made possible by the preparation of the pathogen prototype. *Nature* 2020; 586: 567–571. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Jackson LA, Anderson EJ, Roupael NG, et al. . A SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine - preliminary report. *English N J Med* 2020; 383: 1920-1931. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Mulligan MJ, Lyke KE, Kitchin N, et al. . Phase I / II study of COVID-19 RNA BNT162b1 vaccine in adults. *Nature* 2020; 586: 589-593. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- -. Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, et al. . Safety and efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA COVID 19 vaccine. *English N J Med* 2020; 383: 2603-2615. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)] [This report describes the efficacy and safety data from the Phase III clinical trial for the Pfizer BioNTech COVID-19 mRNA vaccine.](#)
- Baden LR, El Sahly HM, Essink B, et al. . Efficacy and safety of the SARS-CoV-2 mRNA-1273 vaccine. *English J Med* 2021; 384: 403-416. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)] [This report describes the efficacy and safety data from the Phase III clinical trial for the Modern COVID-19 mRNA vaccine.](#)
- Frenck RW, Jr, Klein NP, Kitchin N, et al. . Safety, immunogenicity and efficacy of the COVID-19 BNT162b2 vaccine in adolescents. *N English J Med* 2021; 385: 239-250. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Cardona V, Ansotegui IJ, Ebisawa M, et al. . 2020 World Organization Anaphylaxis Guide. *World J* 2020; 13: allergies 100472. [Article [by Organ](#)] [[PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)] [free](#)
- Rugeberg JU, Gold MS, Bayas JM, et al. . Anaphylaxis: case definition and guidelines for the collection, analysis and presentation of immunization safety data. *vaccine* 2007; 25: 5675–5684. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Shimabukuro TT, Cole M, Su JR. Reports of anaphylaxis after receiving COVID-19 mRNA vaccines in the United States - December 14, 2020 - January 18, 2021. *JAMA* 2021; 325: 1101-1102. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- McNeil MM, DeStefano F. Vaccine associated hypersensitivity. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2018; 141: 463-472. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]

- Stone CA, Jr, Rukasin CRF, Beachkofsky TM, Phillips EJ. Immune-mediated adverse reactions to vaccines. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 2019; 85: 2694-2706. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
This review focuses on excipients that cause allergic reactions to vaccines.
- Cullis PR, Hope MJ. Lipid nanoparticle systems to enable gene therapies. *Mol Ther* 2017; 25: 1467-1475. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Harris JM, chess RB. Effect of pegylation on pharmaceuticals. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 2003; 2: 214-221. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Wylon K, Dolle S, Worm M. Polyethylene glycol as a cause of anaphylaxis. *Allergy Asthma Clin Immunol* 2016; 12:67 PM [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Wenande E, Garvey LH. Immediate-type hypersensitivity to polyethylene glycols: a review. *Clin Exp allergy* 2016; 46: 907-922. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Stone CA, Jr, Liu Y, Relling MV, et al. . Immediate hypersensitivity to polyethylene glycols and polysorbates: more common than we have recognized. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Pract* 2019; 7: 1533-1540. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Sellaturay P, Nasser S, Ewan P. Systemic allergic reactions induced by polyethylene glycol (anaphylaxis). *J Allergy Clin Immunol Practice* 2021; 9: 670-675. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Lu IN, Rutkowski K, Kennard L, et al. . Polyethylene glycol may be the major allergen in the medroxy-progesterone depot *Allergy Clin Immunol Pract* 2020; 8: 3194-3197. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Krantz MS, Liu Y, Phillips EJ, Stone CA, Jr. Contrast anaphylaxis of PEGylated liposomal echocardiogram in a patient with IgE-mediated macrogol allergy. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Pract* 2020; 8: 1416-1419. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Finkelman FD, Khoudoun MV, Stretto R. Human IgE-independent systemic anaphylaxis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2016; 137: 1674-1680. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Jimenez-Rodriguez TW, Garcia-Neuer M, Alenazy LA, Castells M. Anaphylaxis in the 21st century: phenotypes, of biomarker endotypes. *J Asthma allergy* 2018; 11: 121-142. [[PMC article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [free](#) [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Risma KA, Edwards KM, Hummell DS, et al. . Potential mechanisms of anaphylaxis to mRNA vaccines *Allergy COVID-19* . *J Immunol* 2021; *Clin* 17: 2075-2082. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)] [This review reactions in the context of the new COVID-19 mRNA vaccines.](#)
- Bruhns P, Chollet-Martin S. Mechanisms of drug induced human anaphylaxis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2021; 147: 1133-1142. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Cabanillas B, Novak N. Allergy to COVID-19 vaccines: a current update. *Allergol Int* 2021; 70: 313-318. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Menni C, Klaser K, May A, et al. . Vaccine Side Effects and SARS-CoV-2 Infection After Vaccination in UK COVID Symptom Study App Users: A Prospective Observational Study. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2021; 21: 939-949. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Blumenthal KG, Robinson LB, Camargo CA, Jr, et al. . Acute allergic reactions to COVID 19 mRNA vaccines. *JAMA* 2021; 325: 1562-1565. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Banerji A, Wickner PG, Saff R, et al. . mRNA vaccines to prevent COVID-19 disease and reported allergic reactions: current evidence and suggested approach. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Practice* 2021; 9: 1423-1437. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Marcelino J, Farinha S, Silva R, et al. . Non-irritating concentrations for skin testing with SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Practice* 2021; 9: 2476-2477. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Kelso JM. Misdiagnosis of systemic allergic reactions to COVID-19 mRNA vaccines. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol* 2021; 127: 133-134. [Free [article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Perez-Codesido S, Rosado A, Alonso-Diaz-de-Durana MD, et al. . Hypersensitivity to the COVID-19 vaccine confirmed by a positive skin test result: a case report. *J Investig Allergol Clin Immunol* 2021; 31: Online before printing. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]

- Mustafa SS, Ramsey A, Staicu ML. Administration of a second dose of the Moderna COVID-19 vaccine after an immediate hypersensitivity reaction with the first dose: two case reports. *Ann Intern Med* 2021; 174: 1177–1178. [[Free article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Restivo V, Candore G, Barrale M, et al. . Allergy to polyethylene glycol of the recipient of the anti-SARS CoV2 vaccine: a case report of the recipient of a young adult and the management of future exposure to SARS CoV2. *Vaccines (Basel)* 2021; 9: [[Free article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Troelnikov A, Perkins G, Yuson C, et al. . The reactivity of basophils to BNT162b2 is mediated by PEGylated lipid nanoparticles in patients with PEG allergy. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2021; 148: 91-95. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Kelso JM, Greenhawt MJ, Li JT, et al. . Adverse reactions to vaccines, parameter update 2012. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2012; 130: 25-43. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Krantz MS, Bruusgaard-Mouritsen MA, Koo G, et al. . Anaphylaxis at the first dose of SARS CoV-2 mRNA vaccines: do not give up on the second dose! . *Allergy* 2021; 76: 2916–2920. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Greenhawt M, Abrams EM, Shaker M, et al. . The risk of allergic reaction to SARS-CoV-2 vaccines and recommended assessment and management: a systematic review, meta-analysis, GRADE assessment, and an international consensus approach. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Practice* 2021; 9: 3546–3567. [[Free article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Wolfson AR, Robinson LB, Li L, et al. . Allergic reactions to COVID-19 mRNA vaccine at first dose: limited role for skin tests on excipients. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Practice* 2021; 9: 3308.e3–3320.e3. [[Free article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Krantz MS, Kwah JH, Stone CA, Jr, et al. . Evaluation of the safety of the second dose of COVID-19 messenger RNA vaccines in patients with immediate reactions to the first dose. *JAMA Intern Med* 2021. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)] This report describes 189 people from 5 medical centers in the United States who were evaluated for allergic reactions occurring within 4 hours of vaccination against COVID-19 mRNA. It is the largest group described to date and includes 159 individuals who have successfully received a second dose in a patient with urticaria
- Park HJ, Montgomery JR, Boggs NA. Anaphylaxis after COVID-19 vaccine in a patient with cholinergic. *Mil Med* 2021. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 43. Pitlick MM, Sitek AN, Kinate SA, et al. . Skin tests of polyethylene glycol and polysorbate in evaluating reactions to the 2019 coronavirus disease vaccine: early report. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol* 2021; 126: 735–738. [[Free article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Sellaturay P, Nasser S, Islam S, et al. . Polyethylene glycol (PEG) is a cause of Pfizer / BioNTech mRNA COVID-19 vaccine anaphylaxis. *Allergy Clin Exp* 2021; 51: 861–863. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Blumenthal KG, Saff RR, Freeman EE. Large delayed local reactions to SARS-CoV-2 mRNA-1273 vaccine. *N Engl J Med* 2021; 384: 1273-1277. [[Free article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- McMahan DE, Amerson E, Rosenbach M, et al. . Skin reactions reported after Moderna and Pfizer COVID-19 vaccination: a registry-based study of 414 cases. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2021; 85: 46-55. [[Free article from PMC](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]